

International Energy Agency Wind TCP

Task 43: Wind Energy Digitalization

Spring 2021 Meeting

Digital Week II

May 18-20, 2021

Proceedings

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1 Overall goal of the meeting

Since the working groups have put a lot of effort into their topics and gained good progress, the main focus was to receive feedback on the intermediate results through different kinds of interactions. The keynotes and panel discussions should provide perspectives on digitalization of task43-external specialists from other industries to enrich the discussions.

2 Meeting Overview

IEA Wind Task 43 Wind Energy Digitalization held their 3rd general meeting as a digital week from May 18th to 20th 2021. It was an open meeting announced to the public via various means and it found great attention. Nearly 70 participants attended the opening session and around 40 - 60 participants took part in the sessions dedicated to the individual work packages of Task 43.

Jason Fields from National Renewable Energies Lab, operating agent of Task 43, welcomed the audience, gave an overview about the Task 43, and moderated through the whole meeting.

All days started with a key note or a panel discussion respectively. Shuli Goodman from Linux Foundation Energy and Gavin Starks from Icebreaker One presented their views on the state-of-the-art in digitalization and their expectations regarding the further development and next steps needed.

On the first day, a live interview with Daniel Luecht, SiemensGamesa and Khalid Kamhawi, Ithaca Clean Energy allowed a deeper insight for the audience into the current situation with opportunities and barriers of a turbine manufacturing company and a consulting firm offering AI analyses. These findings will enrich the findings from +30 interviews work package 1 “*Roadmap of Digitalization in Wind Energy*” have already conducted.

The third day started with short introductory presentations from and a panel discussion on “*External Perspectives on Digitalization*” with Martin Curley, Health Service Executive-Ireland, Vijayant Kumar, Optum-UnitedHealth Group, and Liz Dennet, Amazon Web Services.

The other six sessions gave space for the work packages to present their intermediate results and to discuss it with the audience. In general, these results drew much attention and started lively discussions with valuable findings for all working groups. The complete agenda for all three days is presented in the annex.

3 External Perspectives

Shuli Goodman (Linux Foundation Energy): “Moving at the speed of technology”

([02_ShuliGoodman-LFEnergy.pdf](#)):

Linux Foundation strongly supports the Open Source approach in combination with space for proprietary developments and business cases. The number of open libraries, which has been increasing for years, seems to confirm this strategy. The LF Energy projects focus on the complete power system unlike Task 43 focussing solely on the wind sector. Task 43 should take this into consideration. (*insert link to Shuli’s presentation / video*)

Gavin Starks (Icebreaker One): “How could Open Energy help the wind sector share data”

(<https://energy.icebreakerone.org/2021/05/19/webinar-iea-wind-task-43-digitalization-in-wind-energy/>):

Icebreaker One’s Open Energy database (energydata.org.uk) is part of the New Energy Digitalisation Taskforce kicked off in the UK and strives for establishing a blueprint. They divide open data and shared data, while open data is free accessible for everybody and shared data is licensed by a legal owner for conditional usage. All docs are licensed using Creative Commons, all codes under MIT license. The database is designed for a maximum interoperability and thus data is findable by metadata.

Vijayant Kumar (Optum-UnitedHealth Group): “Digitalization in Wind Energy and Healthcare: a Jekyll and Hyde story”

([08_VijayantKumar-OptumUnitedHealthGroup_Presentation.pdf](#)):

Optum-United Health Group is tackling at least partly similar issues as the wind industry does. Much of the data is generated or stems from different sources, it is partly structured and partly unstructured and at least for some approaches the return on investment is unclear. Data security and privacy is a hard issue on both sides. Standardization could be one answer, but at the same time standardization can also lead to inflexibility. So, digitalization will require new technology and an appropriate culture of adoption. Sometimes there is no perfect solution.

Liz Dennet (Amazon Web Services): “The OSDU™ Data Platform”

([09_LizDennett-AWS_Presentation.pdf](#)):

Amazon Web Services is supporting the Open Group OSDU™ Data Platform. It is an Open Source, standards-based, technology-agnostic data platform for the energy industry that stimulates innovation, industrializes data management, and reduces time to market for new solutions. The understanding behind this platform is that, for the future energy system there is only one - admittedly complex - interconnected energy data instead of a variety of different sections.

Martin Curley (Health Service Executive-Ireland): “Digitalization in Healthcare in Ireland”

Health Care in Ireland was similarly behind other countries as the wind industry is behind other industries. Digitalization started with a decision: Switch from paper to a fully digital healthcare system. Part of the solution was to setup numerous digital labs distributed over the country and start with different issues at the same time. Digitized data allowed for monitoring patients remotely, especially concerning Covid-19 diseases and newest hardware in the hospitals facilitate generating digital data and communication.

4 Task43 overview and dedicated work package sessions

Jason Fields (National Renewable Energy Laboratory)

[\(01_JasonFields_Intro.pdf\)](#)

Jason Fields from NREL as the Operating Agent of Task 43 Digitalization in Wind Energy welcomed the audience to the third general meeting and introduced the planned agenda for the upcoming meeting. Furthermore, he presented an overview of motivations and goals and the current status of Task 43 before handing over to the first keynote speaker Shuli Goodman from Linux Foundation.

4.1 WP 1 State of the Art and Roadmap

Andrew Bray (MXV Ventures / National Renewable Energy Lab)

[\(WP1 Update for May 2021 Virtual Meeting\)](#)

WP1 has conducted 26 interviews to date with specialists and experts from across various fields of wind digitalization. In addition, a dedicated WP1 survey was conducted resulting in 68 responses. The WP1 group synthesized the responses to come up with initial findings on how to bring about the future of wind digitalization.

The three main **challenges** hindering digitalization in the wind industry revolve around:

- Lack of data accessibility
- Lack of appropriate culture
- Reluctance to share knowledge

At the same time, the three main **opportunities** echoed by respondents to realize the value of digitalization are:

- Availability of good quality data
- Robust for model development
- Communication and open source development

Currently, the group is supporting an extension of the paper "[Grand Challenges in the Science of Wind Energy](#)" [1], which is an effort across several research tasks within the IEA Wind TCP.

Discussion:

Part of the transition will be the generation of good quality data from the moment of generation on in terms of high signal to noise ratio, high temporal resolution, and complete and clean datasets. Another issue is legal aspects of licensing, pricing, second use, etc.

Another part of this is that data generators should think about the potential value of the data for the end-user, not only for the initial user.

4.1.1 Live interview with Khalid Kamhawi (Ithaca Clean Energy) and Daniel Luecht (SiemensGamesa)

[\(04_WP1_Live-Interview.pdf\)](#)

Ithaca Clean Energy would like to encourage the wind industry to intensify its digital transformation. This transformation will be the 3rd industrial revolution and those who don't adapt will suffer. Digital transformation will be a similarly eminent step as the introduction of the internet was in the 2000s.

Siemens Gamesa acknowledges the relevance of digitalization but is reluctant to open data sharing. In the wind industry, the OEMs will suffer most from falling wind turbine prices and thus strongly intend to safeguard their intellectual properties - including data. Yet, they are indeed sharing data in specific projects.

4.2 WP 4 Wind Resource Assessment

Stephen Holleran (BrightWind), Gibson Kersting (RWE Renewables)

[\(2021.05.18 WP4 Slides - Task 43 Meeting 3
IEA Task 43 data standard release v0\)](#)

The process of data processing is labor intensive, error prone, and duplicated for each organization.

The group has been working on an Universal Data Model for Wind Resource Assessment (WRA Data Model), which would save time and effort, reduce risk, allows easier collaboration, enables data science application, and is scalable.

Besides technical data, the data model also captures metadata like measurement metadata, mast metadata, or mounting arrangements. Properly applied, it allows for automated tools like IEC mounting validation, wind vane dead band adjustments, removal of mast shadows and provides a foundation for generation workflows like Machine Learning. It is an open source model under a BSD 3-clause license. Next steps will be adopting the model for remote sensing technologies and solar radiation measurements and incorporating digital calibration certificates.

The first version has been published on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/record/4710169#.YK-eE-dCSCh>

and is available as a JSON file on GitHub: https://github.com/IEA-Task-43/digital_wra_data_standard/tree/v0.1.1-2021.04.

Discussion:

Behind the model's JSON file exists a relational database. Thus, one can translate legacy database systems to the new one if they wish or create translators..

Although, there seems to be a high interest in the data model the next step will be to accelerate more adoption. Currently, only one company (Brightwind) is applying the model with only a few more in development.

For facilitating a verification of digital calibration certificates, APIs for signing and validating certificates are under development, for example by WindGuard, Germany.

4.3 WP 5 & 6 Operations and Maintenance & Digital Life Assessment and Repowering

4.3.1 Work Package 5 Overview

Des Farren (ServusNet Analytics)

[\(07_Des-et-al_WP5_Presentations.pdf\)](#)

The introduction to this work package described the team's parallel approaches of both exploring digitalization capability in O&M as well as the opportunities and challenges in implementing representative digitalization use cases.

Digitalization capability was described in a proposed capability maturity model with initial feedback and calibration carried out as a series of quick surveys during the presentation.

Three representative use cases currently under investigation were presented. The Value of Data use case aims to provide guidance on collecting, curating and utilizing data during the operations phase which will enhance the value ascribed to the wind assets in the context of a financial transaction.

The Risk-Based Maintenance use case explored the development and implementation of a multi-model decision support solution to optimize inspection and repair strategies.

The Digital Twin use case presentation outlined the detailed implementation of a dynamic drive train model and how it can guide critical operation and maintenance decisions.

The common and unique findings from each of these investigations will form the basis of overall recommendations to enhance the level of digitalization in O&M. A more detailed outline of the four presentations is provided below.

4.3.2 Digitalization Maturity Model

Alex Koltsidopoulos (XODUS Group)

The maturity model strives to represent the extent of digitalization, help stakeholders gauge capabilities, highlight potential improvement opportunities and support the elaboration of a roadmap to evolve capabilities.

In a first version, the group has decided to assess the maturity in five different categories:

- Data Availability & Access
- Analytics & Modelling
- Decision Support Applications
- Data & Model Sharing
- Availability of Expertise

The discussions and the feedback from this session will be incorporated in the development of the model as well as in the determination of the current state. In the next step, they will generate a detailed questionnaire, distribute it to a wider audience, and create recommendations. The result will be presented at the upcoming WindEurope Technology Conference in autumn.

Discussion:

The discussions and in-line polling generated insights like:

- Currently, the maturity reaches only level 2, because the industry is fragmented
- The wind industry continues to work with non-interoperable data schemas
- Wind farm owners will not base their decisions solely on decision support tools
- The willingness for data sharing will depend greatly on the scope and purpose of data

4.3.3 Value of Data

Stephen Dictor (Renewable Asset Partners), Altuğ Emiroğlu (ClockworkX)

A lack of good data on an asset may lower its valuation since health of assets and subsystems cannot be readily determined. However, data requirements to support valuation or risk assessment are not clearly defined, recordkeeping may not be an O&M priority and, additionally, incentives are not aligned between prospective investor/ buyer/ insurer and asset owner.

Thus, the group is tackling the questions:

- Which data is most critical to focus on, rather than seek to ‘boil the ocean’?
- What level of granularity and methods of collection & storage are appropriate?
- How can data be best utilized to enhance the value of the assets?

A survey among a limited number of attendees gave a hint to the answer of the first question: Asset operations data, maintenance data, and environmental data are seen as particularly critical, but also pre-construction data, regulatory findings, and community disputes are of high relevance.

The group will put further effort into finding the answers and developing a Wind Owner’s Cookbook to help guide the data collection and utilization strategies.

4.3.4 Risk-Based Maintenance

Alex Byrne (DNV), Josh Paquette (Sandia National Lab), Jannie Sønderkær Nielsen (Aalborg University), Nathan Hoerning (Wisconsin Public Service)

The group is developing a framework for Risk-Based Maintenance (RBM). It is currently focussed on inspection and repair of leading edge erosion of blades but the framework, and subsequent implementation of the constituent model and data components, will act as a template for other scenarios. The initial framework encompasses data requirements, damage growth model, cost model and decision support model and the findings during development will feed into a gap analysis and set of recommendations.

The evaluation will consider a range of decision scenarios around optimizing component inspection and repair strategies and explore the dependence on potential key enablers such as the availability of operational and environmental data or standardized damage classifications.

Discussion:

The team posed a range of questions for discussion and feedback, including:

- The relevance and opportunities of Risk-Based Maintenance
- The preference for higher accuracy/more complex models versus lower accuracy/simpler models.
- The current constraints impacting blade maintenance decisions.

4.3.5 Digital Twin Based Condition Monitoring

Amir Nejad (Norwegian University of Science and Technology)

Main Objective of this group is to establish, employ and demonstrate a systematic approach for Digital Twin based condition monitoring for wind turbines.

O&M costs contribute up to 30% of LCOE in offshore wind turbines, driving demand for increased reliability and lower costs. Fortunately, advances in physics-based modeling, IoT, communication technologies, artificial intelligence and machine learning methods seem promising and could pave the way for more comprehensive solutions, including digital twins.

To that end, this investigation explores the application of digital twins as an integral decision-support tool in ongoing operation and optimisation of wind assets. Specific applications include monitoring and control, estimation of remaining useful life and fault detection, as well as predictive maintenance and scheduling.

A particular challenge is building and validating dynamic models based on limited measurements and data from both physical and simulation-based sensors is explored.

Discussion:

It was highlighted that OEMs already use models in the design phase but it is difficult to apply these in the operation phase as certain properties are unknown. However, it should be possible to share some of the key characteristics of the design models to help inform the development of operations-phase models. There is a role for physics-based modeling but, like any modelling

methodology, it requires sufficient data and a thorough understanding of this, the model and the system functionality.

4.4 TA 2 Data Standards and Data Sharing

Julian Quick (University of Colorado Boulder):

([11_JulianQuick_TA2_presentation.pdf](#))

The development of digitalization in wind energy suffers from a lack of high-quality data, in terms of completeness, availability, accuracy, and format. Sharing data between organizations and applying common standards for data collection and communication could improve the situation.

The identified two generally different obstacles for data sharing

- Differences in semantics
- Data owner's sharing policies

Differences in semantics, e.g. different ontologies and vocabularies, can perhaps be overcome by mapping tables, but often data users will not find existing data due to unclear descriptions of contents and formats. Agreed-upon shared semantics are a promising approach, though this is challenging to organize.

The reluctance of data owners for data sharing partly stems from the unknown value of existing data and from an unclear culture in organizations concerning data sharing and collaboration. Given a metadata standard suggesting an appropriate characterization of existing data, data owners and potential data users could negotiate preconditions and prices for data sharing. Ownership and access could be monitored using a data management system. Then, a kind of market place could emerge. It is possible that a data broker could mediate between the parties.

There are a lot of opportunities concerning metadata in the wind sector.. Thus, the working group is extending an invitation for the "metadata challenge", presented on the WeDoWind platform:

(main site: <https://relight.cloud/space/IEAWindTask43>
register: <https://www.wedowind.ch/blog/ieawindtask43>).

Discussion:

- It seems, the real ownership of data is not always clear
- The value of data will be regarded significantly different depending on the stakeholder
- The "global service protocol" (<https://wind-fgw.de/themes/working-on-the-guidelines/?lang=en>) suggests a standardized digital communication.
- The TA2 working group should try to develop kind of holistic view on the world of standards for data in wind energy
- Anyone who would like to discuss data valuation in more depth, please reach out at <https://www.energydataalliance.com/contact>

4.5 TA 3 Data Science and Open Source

Rob Hammond (NREL), Alex Koltsidopoulos (Xodus Group), Julian Quick (Colorado University):

[\(12_RobHammond_TA3_presentation.pdf\)](#)

Data Science needs expertise in

- Computer Science & Software Engineering
- Mathematics & Statistics
- Domain Knowledge
- Systems Thinking

However, the data itself has no value, the value is generated when analysing and interpreting data and results in context with the domain's particularity. Thus, the intended recommendations of the group will address data scientists, decision makers, as well as everyone in between.

Main recommendation is: before starting with data science consider some ethical topics, like:

- Is the available data appropriate to the issue?
- Are the right stakeholders involved?
- What safeguards exist?
- Is the model audited or will domain experts review decisions?

Once, data science has started, make sure data-informed decision making consists of these three steps:

1. Data selection: Use of available data, innovative thinking & IT infrastructure
2. Model development: Avoid research for the sake of research; create proof of concepts
3. Improved decision making, considering certain challenges:
 - End users and decision makers might not understand/ trust the models
 - Engineering departments may be detached from the rest of the business.
 - Models are usually designed from experts in computational modelling rather than real operations

To discuss and approve recommendations, the working group intends to conduct a hackathon. The preparation is still ongoing, the major task here is to get appropriate free data.

Discussion:

- As long as there remains the need for a human assessment within the process, a real automated decision taking is not possible.
- Rational decision making could also be supported if data-informed models can provide quantitative predictions for the consequences of decision options.

Hackathon:

Still, providing appropriate data is the main issue in preparing the hackathon. On the other hand, more important is who the community is and what the challenge is. If the challenge is of real interest it gets easier to find good data.

5 Lessons learned from ‘digital week’

In general, the virtual meeting worked very well again. However, this time we had nearly 70 attendees with us in the opening session, while we had around 100 attendees a year ago. Similarly, the participation in the other session was a bit less compared to the meeting in 2020.

Admittedly, the save-the-date message was sent a bit late and additionally, the IEA Wind TCP ExCo meeting took place nearly in parallel, and perhaps some interested people had to prepare for the WESC conference in the week after the meeting.

Since it was even hard to find a suitable date among the Task 43 participants, also in future to find a better working week will be difficult. But an earlier announcement would perhaps enable more people to join.

Additionally, the time slots dedicated to the work packages were relatively short and partly quite packed with material. This made it difficult to present and discuss all intermediate results. To dive a bit deeper into details, more time per work package is desirable. Task 43 had addressed this already last year and foreseen separate one day events per work package, but that time there had not been enough results to present and discuss with externals yet.

6 Operating Agents' Contact Details

IEA Wind task 43 is open for interested companies, research organizations, academia etc. from all IEA Wind TCP member countries and organizations. Please contact us via one of the operating agents:

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7 Appendix Digital Week Agenda

		DAY ONE - Digitalization Vision	
Tue 18 th May	08:00-08:15 MDT 16:00-16:15 CEST	Welcome and Task 43 Updates Jason Fields, Operating Agent	
	08:15-09:00 MDT 16:15-17:00 CEST	Keynote: Shuli Goodman, LF Energy "Open Source in Energy"	
	09:00-09:15 MDT 17:00-17:15 CEST	<i>Break</i>	
	09:15-10:00 MDT 17:15-18:00 CEST	Work package #1 <i>Roadmap of Digitalization in Wind Energy -Part 1</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Results 	
	10:00-10:45 MCT 18:00-18:45 CEST	Work package #1 <i>Roadmap of Digitalization in Wind Energy -Part 2</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live interview on the Challenges and Opportunities in Wind Digitalization With Daniel Luecht and Khalid Kamhawi 	
	10:45-11:00 MDT 18:45-19:00 CEST	<i>Break</i>	
	11:00-12:00 MDT 19:00-20:00 CEST	Work package #4 <i>Digital Wind Resource Assessment</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universal Wind Resource Data Model-current progress and next steps 	
	12:00-12:15 MDT 20:00-20:15 CEST	Closing and Day 1 recap	

		DAY TWO - Digital O&M	
Wed 19 th May	08:00-08:15 MDT 16:00-16:15 CEST	Day 2 Welcome and day 1 review Berthold Hahn, Operating Agent	
	08:15-09:00 MDT 16:15-17:00 CEST	Keynote: Gavin Starks, Icebreaker One: "Open Energy Data; States of digitalization, barriers in the different industries"	
	09:00-09:15 MDT 17:00-17:15 CEST	<i>Break</i>	
	09:15-10:15 MDT 17:15-18:15 CEST	Work package #5 <i>Digital Operation and Maintenance -Part 1</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitalization Maturity Model • Value of Data 	
	10:15-10:30 MDT 18:15-18:30 CEST	<i>Break</i>	
	10:30-11:30 MDT 18:30-19:30 CEST	Work package #5 <i>Digital Operation and Maintenance -Part 2</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Based Maintenance • Digital Twin 	
	11:30-11:45 MDT 19:30-19:45 CEST	Closing and Day 2 Recap	

DAY THREE - Data and Data Science		
Thu 20 th May	08:00-08:15 MDT 16:00-16:15 CEST	Day 3 Welcome and day 2 review Jason Fields, Operating Agent
	08:15-09:15 MDT 16:15-17:15 CEST	Keynote: “External Perspectives on Digitalization” Introductory presentations and panel discussion by and with: Martin Curley (Health Service Executive-Ireland) Vijayant Kumar (Optum-UnitedHealth Group) Liz Dennet (Amazon Web Services) Moderator: Michael Purdue (NRG Systems)
	09:15-09:30 MDT 17:15-17:30 CEST	<i>Break</i>
	09:30-10:30 MDT 17:30-18:30 CEST	Technical Area #2 <i>Data Standards and Data Sharing</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared semantics and incentivizing data sharing
	10:30-10:45 MDT 18:30-18:45 CEST	<i>Break</i>
	10:45-11:45 MDT 18:45-19:45 CEST	Technical Area #3 <i>Data Science and Open Source</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data science quick start document and hackathon
	11:45-12:00 MDT 19:45-20:00 CEST	Plenary: Closing